

Life Expectancy in Russian Cities: Why are Some Cities Catching Up While Others are Lagging Behind?

Ekaterina D. Vetrova¹, Natalia M. Kalmykova¹, Mikhail A. Maximov¹

¹ *Lomonosov Moscow State University, Moscow, 119991, Russia*

Received 12 September 2025 ♦ Accepted 27 January 2026 ♦ Published 17 March 2026

Citation: Vetrova ED, Kalmykova NM, Maximov MA (2026) Life Expectancy in Russian Cities: Why are Some Cities Catching Up While Others are Lagging Behind? *Population and Economics* 10(1):227-267. <https://doi.org/10.3897/popecon.10.e172128>

Abstract

This study examines the dynamics of life expectancy at birth (LE) in large Russian cities (with populations exceeding 100,000) from 2012 to 2022. Since 2012, major cities have shown convergence in mortality levels; however, substantial interregional differences persist. The aim of this study is to identify mortality patterns in Russian cities, to distinguish leading, catching-up, and lagging cities in terms of life expectancy dynamics, and to describe the socio-economic profiles associated with each group. The analysis employs the delta convergence method, which makes it possible to classify cities according to changes in life expectancy relative to the national average.

In the pre-pandemic period (2012–2019), convergence in life expectancy was driven primarily by cities with populations between 100,000 and 500,000 that are not administrative centers. The main differences between leading and lagging cities are explained by mortality in the 35–64 age group. Cities in which convergence slowed and life expectancy growth lagged during this period include large cities and regional capitals characterized by weaker economic performance and poorer environmental conditions. The COVID-19 pandemic disrupted the convergence process, primarily by slowing the decline in mortality in catching-up cities.

Keywords

life expectancy in Russian cities, mortality convergence, delta convergence, socioeconomic determinants of mortality

JEL codes: I14, J10, J11

Introduction

Inequality in mortality rates across Russian regions has been documented by numerous studies (Andreev et al. 2014; Danilova 2017; Shchur and Timonin 2020; Nikoloski et al. 2023; Timonin et al. 2017). This inequality has persisted over the past two decades and, in some

regions, has even increased. In 2022, life expectancy at birth ranged from 66.2 years in the Chukotka Autonomous Okrug to 78.2 years in Moscow. The north-eastern mortality gradient – an increase in life expectancy from the north-east to the south-west – also remains pronounced (Meslé and Shkolnikov 1999).

At the same time, analyses of the causes of persistent regional mortality inequality in Russia have been conducted mainly at the regional level. Only in the last 15 years have studies emerged that examine centre–periphery differences in mortality within regions (Shchur and Timonin 2020; Timonin et al. 2020; Fattakhov and Mironova 2022), urban–rural mortality differentials (Shchur et al. 2021), and mortality differences among populations of million-plus cities (Shchur 2018). A substantial share of the regional population lives in cities with populations of 100,000 or more (52.5%). We assume that these cities either contribute to a life expectancy advantage relative to the regional average or, conversely, account for a regional lag. Accordingly, such cities constitute the focus of this study.

The determinants of territorial differences in life expectancy have attracted considerable scholarly attention. However, the sets of explanatory factors used in empirical studies vary and are typically constrained by data availability at a given administrative level – municipalities, cities of different population sizes, or regions (oblasts, krais, republics). These determinants include demographic factors, such as age-specific mortality patterns and cause-of-death structures, as well as socio-economic factors that have contributed to differentiation in life expectancy at birth, including during the COVID-19 pandemic (Kolosnitsyna and Chubarov 2022).

A broader conceptual classification of factors influencing life expectancy at birth is proposed by Adler and Newman (2002), who distinguish three main groups: socio-economic, medical-demographic, and environmental factors. Behavioural factors also play a significant role, particularly alcohol consumption, smoking, diet quality, and attitudes toward regular physical activity (Denisova 2018).

A number of studies have demonstrated that life expectancy at birth is strongly influenced by the educational attainment of the population. In Russia, the life expectancy of individuals without completed secondary education declined both during periods of crisis (Shkolnikov et al. 2006) and during periods when life expectancy among those with secondary and higher education was increasing (Pyankova and Fattakhov 2017; Meara et al. 2008). Changes in the educational structure of the population are therefore reflected in mortality patterns (Kharkova et al. 2017).

Differentiation in life expectancy is also significantly shaped by population income levels (Karlsson et al. 2010). Groups with higher socioeconomic status tend to have better health outcomes and, consequently, longer life expectancy (Zimmer and Amornsirisomboon 2001; Camargos et al. 2007; Jasilionis and Shkolnikov 2016; Mackenbach et al. 2019). Moreover, income affects life expectancy inequality not only between countries but also across regions within the same country (Sede and Ohemeng 2015; Hoi et al. 2009). Researchers have also identified a relationship between losses in life expectancy and income inequality, both at the cross-country level (Shkolnikov et al. 2011) and within Russia at the interregional level (Andreev and Shkolnikov 2018). Notably, while no significant association has been found between average income levels and life expectancy across Russian regions, a robust relationship has been observed between life expectancy and income inequality, as measured by the Gini coefficient.

Many authors argue that the primary factor determining population health – and, consequently, life expectancy as a health outcome – is the performance of the healthcare system.

Since direct measures of healthcare quality are often unavailable, a number of studies use financial indicators as proxies, such as healthcare expenditure as a share of GDP or per capita healthcare spending (Asiskovitch 2010; Heuvel and Olaroiu, 2017).

The relationship between life expectancy and healthcare expenditure is, however, ambiguous. On the one hand, higher healthcare spending is associated with improvements in population health. On the other hand, several studies have identified a reverse relationship, whereby increases in life expectancy lead to higher healthcare expenditures, reflecting greater demand for medical services at older ages (Andreev and Shkolnikov 2018; Heuvel and Olaroiu 2017).

Some studies employ the share of the urban population and population density as proxy variables for the quality and accessibility of healthcare services. These factors are particularly relevant for geographically large countries, including Russia (Ivanov and Suvorov 2003; Anyanwu and Erhijakpor 2009). In addition, spatial and geographical analyses have examined the effectiveness of healthcare systems at the regional level (see, for example, Panin et al. (2023)). Several authors (Revich et al. 2019) report a significant association between the share of healthcare expenditure in the economy and life expectancy in cities with populations exceeding one million. It can be hypothesised that a similar relationship exists in administrative centres with smaller populations.

Regarding environmental determinants, an unfavourable environmental situation – characterised by air, water, and soil pollution – can lead to increased mortality from chronic diseases (WHO 2018). Atmospheric emissions contribute to additional deaths, which, according to estimates for Russia, account for 3–5% of total mortality (Revich 2005).

The present study aims to create a socio-economic profile of cities belonging to different groups with respect to the acceleration or deceleration of life expectancy convergence.

To achieve this objective, the following tasks were addressed:

1. Identification of groups of cities with different dynamics of the life expectancy at birth gap relative to the average value for all cities with populations of 100,000 or more;
2. Analysis of the age structure and cause-of-death composition of mortality in different groups of cities;
3. Identification, based on a review of the literature, of key socio-economic determinants that may influence age- and cause-specific mortality patterns in urban populations and, consequently, determine cities' membership in different groups depending on whether the gap in life expectancy at birth relative to the average is narrowing or widening.

We hypothesise that a higher level of socio-economic development of a city – measured by indicators such as per capita income, the share of dilapidated housing, and the capacity of outpatient healthcare facilities – increases the likelihood that the city belongs to the group characterised by accelerated growth in life expectancy. The selection of variables was determined by the availability of data for Russian cities.

Data

This paper analyses factors influencing the convergence and divergence of life expectancy at birth in Russian cities with populations of 100,000 or more between 2012 and 2022. As of 1 January 2022, the population of these cities accounted for 52.5% of the total population of Russia.

To identify cities with lagging indicators and to analyse the reasons for this lag, data from the Federal State Statistics Service (Rosstat) were used, along with data from the Database of Indicators of Municipalities of Russia, processed within the framework of the Infrastructure of Scientific Research Data (INID) projects¹, and the Roshydromet database State of Air Pollution in Russian Cities since 2007 (To Be Precise edition)².

At present, the concept of a “large city” is not legally defined in Russia. In line with the typology of the Urban Development Code, this study focuses on big cities (more than 100,000 but fewer than 250,000 inhabitants), large cities (more than 250,000 but fewer than 1 million), largest cities (from 1 to 3 million), and super-large cities (more than 3 million inhabitants). Cities in these categories are considered broadly comparable in terms of socio-economic development and infrastructure. The largest and super-large cities are combined into a single category of million-plus cities.

The development of absolute mortality indicators – specifically, the distribution of deaths by sex, age group, and cause of death – and the calculation of relative mortality rates for cities with populations of 100,000 or more, as well as for administrative centres of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation, were not carried out by Federal State Statistics Service (Rosstat) prior to 2011. Therefore, this study relies on life expectancy data for the period 2011–2022 obtained from the Mortality and Life Expectancy Tables (Form 3TS), as well as data from the tables Distribution of Deaths by Sex, Age Group, and Cause of Death (Form C51) and Average Annual Population by Sex and Age (Form 4PH) for Russian cities with populations exceeding 100,000.

Using data for cities with populations of 100,000 or more, we compared the dynamics of life expectancy in each city relative to the average level for all cities in this population category. In addition, deviations in life expectancy for individual cities from the sample average were decomposed by age group and cause of death in order to identify the main contributors to inter-city differences in mortality.

According to data from the Federal State Statistics Service (Rosstat), in 2011 there were 164 cities in Russia with populations exceeding 100,000. Summary statistics by city are presented in Table 1. The full list of cities is provided in the Appendix (Table A1).

In several cities – Leninsk-Kuznetsky and Mezhdurechensk in the Kemerovo Oblast, as well as Sarapul in the Udmurt Republic – the population fell below 100,000 after 2011. Such cities are excluded from the Rosstat dataset, making it impossible to track life expectancy dynamics for them over time.

An additional data limitation concerns the city of Balashikha. In 2015, the city of Zheleznodorozhny was incorporated into Balashikha, rendering observations before and after 2015 incomparable. After excluding these cases, the final analytical sample comprises 159 cities whose populations exceeded 100,000 during the period 2011–2022.

No further adjustments were made for changes in city boundaries within the scope of this study; life expectancy indicators were used as published by Rosstat. This constitutes a potential limitation of the analysis.

1 Database of indicators of municipalities: combined and processed data for 2006–2020 // Rosstat; processing: Vedenkov M.V., Komin M.O., Tsygankov M.V., Infrastructure of scientific research data. ANO “CPUR”, 2022. Access: License CC BY-SA. Posted: September 28, 2020 (v.2.0, from January 27, 2022). (Dataset link: <http://data.rcsi.science/data-catalog/datasets/115/>)

2 Air pollution levels in Russian cities since 2007//Roshydromet; processed “To Be Precise”, 2023. Terms of use: Creative Commons BY 4.0. URL: https://tochno.st/datasets/air_cities

Table 1. Distribution of large Russian cities by population in 2011

Population size	Number of cities, total	Including administrative centers of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation
Big cities (population between 100,000 and 250,000)	90	12
Large cities (population between 250,000 and 1 million)	62	49
Over 1 million	12	12

Source: authors' compilation based on Rosstat data

To describe the socio-economic situation of cities, data from two databases were used: “Database of indicators of municipalities of Russia for 2006–2020 (beta version)” processed by INID and “State of air pollution in Russian cities since 2007” (Roshydromet) processed by the “To be precise” project.

For evaluation of the income level of the population the weighted average monthly salary was used. Also, the level of life expectancy is likely related to the unemployment rate, but the available statistics for cities only reflect the number of people officially registered at the labour exchange. This indicator cannot be correct, since not all unemployed people register with the labour exchange. There are serious risks of underestimating the indicator. The share of emergency housing in the total housing area in the city is used as an additional indicator reflecting the standard of living of the population.

The following indicators are used as indicators of the healthcare system: number of mid-level medical personnel per 1000 population, capacity of outpatient clinics (visits per shift) per 1000 population, number of hospital beds per 1000 population. Given the limited data collected across Russian cities, these characteristics were chosen as indicators of the population's provision of medical care. We assume that administrative centers of federal subjects are characterized by a higher provision of medical services than cities that are not centers, that is, the selected indicators will be higher.

As a measure of environmental quality was the level of air pollution in cities was used, assessed within the framework of Roshydromet's atmospheric air monitoring. Atmospheric emissions affect public health more than other polluting waste (Revich 2018).

Methods

Delta convergence

Based on a review of studies on convergence (Heichel et al. 2005), four key methods are commonly identified: beta, sigma, gamma, and delta convergence.

The beta convergence model is based on the hypothesis that cities with lower initial life expectancy levels should experience larger increases in life expectancy than cities with higher initial levels. In other words, lagging cities gradually approach the life expectancy levels of leading cities.

Sigma convergence refers to a reduction in the variation of life expectancy over time, indicating a decrease in differences between cities.

The delta convergence method is typically applied to small samples to evaluate mortality rates, social policies, or other characteristics of individual countries relative to an ideal development model (Heichel et al. 2005; Noy and Sprague-Jones 2016; Hrzic et al. 2023). Our study of Russian cities with populations over 100,000 also involves a relatively small sample: 159 cities observed from 2011 to 2022.

Beta and sigma convergence are currently the most widely used approaches among researchers. For example, Edwards (2011) uses an approach similar to beta convergence to analyze changes in life expectancy across countries between 1970 and 2000. This method examines the change in a country's life expectancy relative to its previous year. A negative slope indicates convergence: the higher the initial life expectancy, the smaller the subsequent increase. Edwards also employs classical inequality measures, including standard deviation, Gini index, interquartile range, and Theil index.

Edwards (2011) finds evidence of convergence in life expectancy at birth globally between 1970 and 2000, with notable exceptions such as the impact of HIV in African countries and increased mortality in former Soviet republics following the USSR's collapse. However, convergence during this period was largely driven by reductions in infant mortality. When assessing life expectancy in adulthood, conclusions are less clear and depend significantly on the chosen metric. The study also identifies convergence within countries.

Worldwide mortality inequality has been primarily explained by differences between countries. These differences are particularly pronounced in industrialized countries when inequality is measured through the dispersion of life expectancy at age 10 (Edwards and Tuljapurkar 2005). Although average life expectancy at age 10 increased in these countries from the 1960s to the 2000s, the variance of this indicator also grew significantly. This approach to measuring inequality is conceptually similar to sigma convergence.

Using data from European countries and municipalities for the period 2003–2012, convergence in the population aging process was studied (Kashnitsky et al. 2017). To assess the statistical significance of the results, the authors also applied beta convergence methods. The overall dependency ratio was used as an indicator of population aging.

At the country level, a study of convergence in fertility, mortality, urbanization, and population aging was conducted for the provinces of China (Kalabikhina et al. 2020). The findings regarding mortality were mixed. In terms of infant mortality, inter-provincial differentiation remained high, and neither sigma nor beta convergence was detected. However, with respect to life expectancy, the provinces exhibited convergence from 1990 to 2010, followed by an increase in variation between 2010 and 2015. This example highlights the cyclical nature of the convergence process.

In a previous study using Russian data (Vetrova and Kalmykova 2024), we demonstrated convergence in life expectancy levels among large Russian cities from 2012 to 2019. Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, major Russian cities were converging in life expectancy. Significant beta convergence was observed, indicating higher rates of life expectancy growth in cities with initially low values. Additionally, significant sigma convergence was detected, reflecting a reduction in the spread of life expectancy values over time (a decrease in the standard deviation). However, during the pandemic period (2020–2021) and in 2022, beta convergence slowed, and sigma convergence became statistically insignificant. These results suggest that the pandemic slowed the convergence of life expectancy among Russian cities.

This study examines changes in city-level life expectancy using the delta convergence method, which enables the classification of cities according to their contribution to overall

convergence, thereby identifying leading cities and those where the convergence process is slowing.

Convergence is understood as the reduction of differences in life expectancy between cities, reflecting their movement toward the average level for all cities with populations of 100,000 or more. Following Hrzic et al. (2023), cities are divided into four groups based on the dynamics of life expectancy at birth relative to the average:

- a) Group of increasing advantage: cities where life expectancy was above the average at the beginning of the period, and by 2019 the gap had further increased;
- b) Group of decreasing advantage: cities where life expectancy was above average in 2012, but this advantage had decreased by 2019;
- c) Group of decreasing disadvantage: cities where life expectancy at birth was below average in 2012, but by 2019 the lag had narrowed;
- d) Group of increasing disadvantage: cities where life expectancy at birth was below average in 2012, and by 2019 the lag had increased.

The classification is based on data up to 2019, since life expectancy dynamics changed substantially during the COVID-19 pandemic (Vetrova and Kalmykova 2024).

The dynamics of life expectancy in each group relative to the average city-level life expectancy are illustrated schematically in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Dynamics of city-level life expectancy in each group relative to the average life expectancy. *Source:* authors’ calculations based on Hrzic et al. (2023).

The delta convergence approach allows addressing several key questions:

1. Determine which group contains the largest number of cities. In terms of life expectancy growth, the most favourable scenarios occur when groups (a) or (c) predominate. The numerical dominance of group (a) indicates that most cities already experience a stable increase in life expectancy. While some individual cities may slow overall convergence, their number is relatively small. The predominance of group (c) reflects active convergence, in which lagging cities are reducing the gap with leading cities, as life expectancy in these cities grows faster than in the leading cities.

2. Identify cities where the lag in life expectancy increased despite overall growth (2012–2019; group d), thereby slowing convergence. These cities require special attention in socio-economic policy development, as they have not approached the levels of the leading cities. The study also considers the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on cities in each group.

Methodology for determining mortality characteristics in groups of cities

To identify the causes of death that contribute to either the convergence or the deceleration of life expectancy in large cities, a decomposition of the deviation of city-level life expectancy from the average life expectancy was performed by age and cause of death for the period 2011–2019, using the life expectancy decomposition method (Andreev 1982).

To calculate average age-specific death rates, as well as age-specific death rates by cause, the number of deaths and population by age group were aggregated across all major cities in the sample, and death rates were computed for five-year age intervals. Based on these calculations, a model of an “average city” with a population of 100,000 was constructed, which served as a reference for comparison with all other cities in the sample.

The decomposition was initially conducted using five-year age intervals, after which results were combined into broader age groups: 0–14, 15–34, 35–64, and 65+ years. To decompose differences in life expectancy by cause of death, three major classes of causes were selected, covering the majority of deaths in Russia:

- II Neoplasms
- IX Diseases of the circulatory system
- XX External causes of death

In addition, a fourth class was included:

- I Infectious diseases

Although deaths from infectious diseases are less numerous than those from digestive or respiratory diseases, they were included alongside the three most common causes because, despite their smaller share in the standardized death rate, mortality from infectious diseases increased until 2019 and exhibited substantial regional variation (Astrelin 2020).

All remaining causes of death were grouped together. The decomposition was performed separately for men and women.

Methodology for determining the socio-economic portrait of groups of cities

To determine the socio-economic profile of large cities within each group, average values of socio-economic development indicators, as well as population size, were calculated. For each group, the shares of administrative centres, large cities, and cities with over one million inhabitants were also computed.

The average value of each indicator within a group was compared with the corresponding average for all major cities in the same year. The percentage deviation of a group indicator from the national average was calculated as:

$$\Delta_i = (x_{ij} - x_j) / x_j \times 100\%,$$

where x_{ij} is the average value of the socio-economic indicator for cities in group i in year j , and x_j is the average value of the same indicator for all major Russian cities in year j .

Between 2011 and 2019, life expectancy at birth in Russian cities showed steady convergence. However, during 2020–2021, the COVID-19 pandemic and the associated socio-economic crisis constituted an exogenous shock, affecting both mortality levels and structure as well as the socio-economic environment. This disruption of long-term trends makes it impossible to identify consistent patterns in data beyond 2019.

Results

Classification of cities based on the delta convergence approach

Using the delta convergence method, cities were classified into four groups (Table 2). The largest group, comprising 35% of cities, was the “decreasing disadvantage” group, reflecting positive convergence dynamics up to 2019.

Table 2. Characteristics of groups of cities with populations of 100,000 or more according to life expectancy trends

	Increasing advantage (a)	Diminishing advantage (b)	Decreasing disadvantage (c)	Increasing disadvantage (d)
Number of cities in the group	41	20	56	42
Share among all cities	26%	13%	35%	26%
Cities with a population of over a million	6	1	1	4
Large cities (population between 250,000 and 1 million)	14	10	15	23
Big cities (population between 100,000 and 250,000)	21	9	40	15
Number of administrative centers	21	10	16	26

Source: authors' calculations based on Rosstat data

The “decreasing disadvantage” group, which primarily drives convergence, is largely composed of cities with populations between 100,000 and 250,000. These cities are rarely administrative centres of their regions, with only 16 out of 56 cities (29%) holding such a status.

In contrast, the “increasing disadvantage” group, which slows down convergence, includes four cities with populations exceeding one million – Samara, Novosibirsk, Omsk, and Chelyabinsk – and 23 cities with populations from 250,000 to 1 million. The proportion of administrative centres in this group is higher, with 26 out of 42 cities (62%). This pattern can be partly explained by selective migration, whereby people from smaller towns move to large cities in search of medical care, which can lead to higher mortality in these urban centers (Kovanova and Badmaeva 2018).

The geographical distribution of cities by group is shown in Figure 2. A complete list of cities, including their assigned scenario and region, is provided in the Appendix (Table A1).

No clear geographical patterns were observed in the distribution of city groups. Cities in the least prosperous “increasing disadvantage” group are found across most regions, and within a single region, cities from different groups often coexist. However, cities in the “growing advantage” group, where the gap with the average life expectancy is narrowing, are predominantly located in the western part of the country, consistent with the previously documented north-eastern gradient in mortality.

Figure 2. Geographical distribution of cities across the four groups based on life expectancy dynamics. *Source:* authors’ compilation.

It can be assumed that a city’s lagging position is more closely related to its own socio-economic characteristics than to the average level of economic development in the region. An exception to this pattern is the Republic of Dagestan, which is represented by four large cities, all of which belong to the “increasing advantage” group. However, as noted by several researchers, results regarding life expectancy in the Caucasus republics should be interpreted with caution (Andreev 2012; Shchur et al. 2021; Mkrtchyan 2012; Vetrova and Kalmykova 2024).

Age differences in mortality across city groups

We identified four broad age groups based on their contributions to life expectancy at birth: children (0–14 years), young working-age adults (15–34 years), older working-age adults (35–64 years), and older adults (65+ years). Although the 65+ age group may seem broad, this aggregation is appropriate for two reasons. First, the focus of this study is on the contribution of each age group to the increase or decrease in the gap in life expectancy, rather than a detailed analysis of mortality patterns at each individual age. Second, in most regions – with the exception of Moscow and St. Petersburg – life expectancy at ages above 65 showed either no increase or only a minimal increase during the study period (Safarova et al. 2018; Shchur and Timonin 2020).

The 0–14 age group contributes minimally to intercity differences in life expectancy across all cities in the sample. The corresponding results are presented in Figure 3, which illustrates the contribution of causes of death to deviations in life expectancy relative to the average for all cities with populations of 100,000 or more.

Figure 3. Decomposition of the gap in life expectancy at birth between large cities and the overall average by cause of death, ages 0–14, 2012–2019. *Source:* authors’ compilation based on Rosstat data. *Note:* Positive columns indicate that mortality from a given cause contributes to life expectancy in a city group exceeding the overall average. Negative columns indicate that mortality from a given cause contributes to a lag in life expectancy relative to the overall average.

In the figure, columns with positive values indicate that mortality from a given cause in a group of cities is lower than the average, meaning that life expectancy in that group exceeds the overall average by the value shown due to reduced mortality from that cause. Conversely, negative values indicate higher-than-average mortality for that cause, which reduces life expectancy in the group relative to the average.

In this age group, by 2019, mortality rates were generally low. The combined contribution of all causes of death to deviations in life expectancy for men in cities did not exceed one year (Figure 3). In some years (2013–2015), women exhibited notable deviations in the contributions of individual causes relative to the average; however, these deviations largely compensated for one another, as an increase in mortality for one cause was offset by a comparable decrease for another. For example, in 2013, mortality from other causes increased sharply in the decreasing disadvantage group, but mortality from external causes decreased by a similar magnitude.

Due to the small number of deaths in these age groups, even minor fluctuations can significantly affect the observed mortality structure. This effect is particularly pronounced for

women, whose mortality rates in childhood and adolescence are lower than those of men, likely due to more pronounced self-preservation behaviors (Gazizullina 2018).

At the level of five-year age groups, the dominant causes of death that contribute to advantages for leading cities and disadvantages for lagging cities are also unstable, varying from year to year (Appendix, Figures A1 and A2). Appendix Figure A9 presents data for women aged 0–14 years with the 2013 outlier excluded, providing a clearer representation of the cause-of-death structure in the remaining years.

In the 15–34 age group, convergence is observed, primarily driven by a reduction in mortality from external causes in lagging cities (Figure 4). This effect is particularly pronounced in the decomposition of life expectancy for men, where the decreasing disadvantage group approaches the average largely due to the decline in mortality from external causes. For women, this trend is less pronounced but remains observable.

The influence of infectious diseases is also notable in this age group. The contribution of infectious diseases to the life expectancy advantage in the increasing advantage and de-

Figure 4. Decomposition of the gap in life expectancy at birth between large cities and the overall average by cause of death, 15–34 years, 2012–2019. *Source:* authors’ compilation based on Rosstat data. *Note:* positive columns indicate the contribution of the cause of death to the excess of life expectancy of a group of cities over the average level. Negative columns indicate the contribution of the cause of death to the lag in the life expectancy of a group of cities from the average level.

creasing advantage groups remains significant through 2019 for both men and women. This pattern is likely related to the HIV epidemic. Among the age groups considered, HIV-related mortality increased continuously from 2012 to 2017, with the epidemic exhibiting substantial regional variation across Russia (Astrelin 2020; Savina et al. 2023).

In the 35–64 age group, the contribution to deviations in life expectancy from the average – both positive and negative – is greater than in younger age groups and remains largely unchanged through 2019. Consequently, convergence in this age group is slower, as confirmed by previous studies (Vetrova and Kalmykova 2024). According to Shchur et al. (2023), the probability of dying during working age in Russia remains high compared to leading countries worldwide, and these losses remained virtually unchanged from 2014 to 2019. This age group thus has the greatest potential for mortality reduction.

The primary cause of differences between city groups in this age range is diseases of the circulatory system (see Figure 5), which is also evident when analyzed at the level of five-

Figure 5. Decomposition of the gap in life expectancy at birth between large cities and the overall average by cause of death, ages 35–64, 2012–2019. *Source:* authors’ compilation based on Rosstat data. *Note:* Positive columns indicate that mortality from a given cause contributes to life expectancy in a city group exceeding the overall average. Negative columns indicate that mortality from a given cause contributes to a lag in life expectancy relative to the overall average

year age intervals (Appendix, Figures A4 and A5). For men, mortality from external causes also makes a noticeable contribution.

The high and increasing contribution of infectious disease mortality to life expectancy differences in this age group is largely attributable to HIV. Since the early 2010s, HIV-related mortality has been steadily increasing in age groups of 45 years and older, whereas in the 35–44 age group, mortality began to decline after 2017 (Maximov 2025). This pattern likely explains the stabilization in the contribution of infectious diseases to differences in life expectancy after 2017. Cities with initially high life expectancy apparently experienced lower HIV-related mortality, so the stabilization of infectious disease contributions coincided with a reduction in mortality in the 35–44 age group.

In the older age group (65+), diseases of the circulatory system are the dominant contributor to the life expectancy advantage of cities in the increasing advantage group relative to the overall average (Figure 6). This pattern is observed for both men and women. Mortality from neoplasms also plays a notable role among men: cities in the increasing advantage

Figure 6. Decomposition of the gap in life expectancy at birth between large cities and the overall average by cause of death, ages 65 and older, 2012–2019. *Source:* authors’ compilation based on Rosstat data. *Note:* Positive columns indicate that mortality from a given cause contributes to life expectancy in a city group exceeding the overall average. Negative columns indicate that mortality from a given cause contributes to a lag in life expectancy relative to the overall average.

group further increase their lead over the average in part due to lower mortality from this class of diseases.

When examining five-year age intervals in the “decreasing disadvantage” group, a shift in the dominant causes of death is observed in older age groups, which contribute most to the lag relative to the average (Figures A3–A8 in the Appendix). The dynamics of cause-of-death structure in this group show a transition from the high significance of circulatory system diseases in 2012–2013 to the predominance of other, less common causes in later years. This shift may be partly explained by changes in death-coding practices (Andreev 2016; Marychev et al. 2025). Notably, the reduction in the life expectancy gap occurs relatively evenly across all age groups.

Table 3 presents a summary of the contribution of different age and sex groups and causes of death to the lag in life expectancy relative to the average. The leading causes of the lag are similar in the “decreasing disadvantage” and “increasing disadvantage” groups; however, in the latter group, no reduction in the contribution of these causes is observed over time.

Differences in the dynamics of life expectancy among city groups may be linked to variations in their socio-economic development, as reflected in their socio-economic profiles.

Table 3. Key characteristics of the structure of causes of death influencing the lag in life expectancy of cities relative to the average.

Age groups	Women	Men
0-14 years	There are no significant differences, mortality within the group is close to 0	Significant differences between groups. The main reason for the lag is mortality from external causes.
15-34 years old	Slightly behind average. Infectious diseases are more common in lagging groups	Significant contribution of infectious diseases
35-64 years old	The main reason for the delay is DCS	Large differences between groups. The main reasons for the delay are the DCS and external factors
65+ years old	The main reason for the delay is DCS	The main reason for the delay is DCS, the second is neoplasms

Source: authors’ compilation

Socioeconomic portrait of cities

Despite the limited availability of socio-economic data at the city level, the analysis allows for the identification of characteristic features of each group. Figure 7 presents the deviations of group-level indicators from the average values for all cities in the sample. A value of zero corresponds to the annual average for all cities. Positive values indicate that a group’s indicator exceeds the average for all major cities in the country in the given year.

The increasing advantage group includes a high proportion of regional administrative centers and cities with populations exceeding one million. Population incomes, estimated using average nominal wages, consistently exceeded the average throughout 2011–2019. Household sizes are slightly larger than average, but the difference is not substantial.

Figure 7. Deviations of socio-economic indicators in city groups from the average values for all major cities in Russia, 2011–2019. *Source:* authors’ compilation based on the Database of Municipalities and the Roshydromet database.

The share of emergency housing, used as an indicator of living standards and economic well-being, began to exceed the average significantly by 2015, likely due to the introduction of additional criteria for classifying housing as emergency in 2013. Performance indicators of medical institutions in these cities are generally above average, particularly the number of mid-level medical personnel and hospital beds per 1,000 population. Outpatient clinic capacity, measured by visits per 1,000 population, is slightly below average.

Environmental conditions, assessed through air pollution levels, were consistently better than average from 2012 to 2019, with the advantage in air quality increasing further by 2018–2019.

The decreasing advantage group is approximately half the size of the other groups. It often includes regional administrative centers, typically cities with populations between 500,000 and 1 million. Average wages in these cities remained below the national average throughout the period under consideration. The proportion of emergency housing is also below average. Among medical indicators, only the number of mid-level medical personnel per 1,000 population exceeds the average. Air pollution levels in these cities are below average.

The increasing disadvantage group is primarily composed of cities that are not regional administrative centers, with populations ranging from 100,000 to 500,000. Average wages in these cities were slightly above the overall average for large cities from 2012 to 2019. The share of emergency housing remains above average. Medical indicators in these cities are close to the national average.

The increasing disadvantage group, like the increasing advantage group, frequently includes administrative centers. This group also comprises cities with populations exceeding one million, as well as cities with populations over 500,000. Wages in these cities are consistently below the average for all major cities, while air pollution levels are higher. The proportion of emergency housing is significantly below the national average. Among medical indicators, the capacity of outpatient departments per 1,000 population is above the average for large cities in the country.

Thus, cities with unfavorable life expectancy dynamics (the decreasing advantage and increasing disadvantage groups) are characterized by lower wages, consistent with the positive association between higher income levels and increased life expectancy. Interestingly, these same groups of cities also exhibit a lower share of emergency housing, a pattern that requires further investigation and cannot be unambiguously interpreted.

Life expectancy is predictably lower in cities with higher levels of air pollution. In the increasing advantage group, a decline in air pollution by 2019 was accompanied by a rapid increase in life expectancy.

Differences in health care system indicators across city groups suggest the presence of a feedback effect. In cities with lagging life expectancy, the capacity of outpatient facilities is higher than in cities with an advantage in life expectancy, potentially reflecting a response to greater population health needs. A similar pattern is observed for hospital beds: cities in the increasing disadvantage group have a higher-than-average number of beds, likely due to unfavorable mortality and morbidity trends and the need to expand medical care. Conversely, cities in which life expectancy is approaching the average (the decreasing advantage and decreasing disadvantage groups) have fewer hospital beds than average.

Despite higher facility capacity, the number of mid-level medical personnel per 1,000 population is lower in cities with low life expectancy. This indicates that even with expanded infrastructure, these cities experience a shortage of medical personnel, which may limit the effectiveness of healthcare delivery.

During periods of stable growth in life expectancy (2012–2019) in Russian cities with populations of 100,000 or more, life expectancy dynamics generally reflect a convergence process. However, a subset of cities continues to lag behind the average life expectancy for large cities, including both administrative centers and non-administrative cities. Notably, this lag persists in several cities with populations exceeding one million (Samara, Chelyabinsk, Novosibirsk, Omsk), which, in principle, are expected to benefit from more developed healthcare systems and generally more favourable socio-economic conditions compared to smaller cities or those without administrative status.

In these cities, even during years of overall positive trends, the expected increase in life expectancy does not materialize. This suggests that targeted socio-economic policies are required to raise life expectancy, informed by a detailed analysis of the underlying causes of the lag – not only in non-administrative cities but also in large regional centers that are falling behind.

Changes in life expectancy trends during the COVID-19 pandemic

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the dynamics of life expectancy underwent significant changes (Figure 8). Cities in the increasing advantage group prior to 2019 retained their position by 2022, although the growth in their advantage ceased. Cities that exhibited a decreasing advantage relative to the average before 2019 also maintained their relative position; however, the dispersion within this group had increased markedly by 2022.

The decreasing disadvantage group of cities experienced the greatest impact during the period from 2019 to 2022. The range of life expectancy values within this group widened considerably, as did the gap between the group median and the overall average for all cities. The average life expectancy in these catch-up cities fell below pre-pandemic levels and, by 2022, had not returned to its previous values. Prior to the pandemic, life expectancy in these cities had been gradually approaching the overall average, with the gap narrowing; however, by 2022, these cities were once again in lagging positions.

Cities that were already lagging behind before 2019 proved relatively more resilient to external shocks. This can be partly attributed to a “low base” effect: life expectancy in these cities was already low prior to the pandemic. By 2022, the gap between the median life expectancy in this group and the overall city average had effectively disappeared, primarily as a result of declines in cities with higher pre-pandemic life expectancy rather than improvements in the lagging cities themselves.

The convergence process slowed because catch-up cities suffered the most from the external shock. Nevertheless, even in leading cities, the growth of life expectancy slowed.

Our findings indicate that a city’s inclusion among large cities, or its status as an administrative centre, does not automatically guarantee high life expectancy or a favourable position in terms of life expectancy growth relative to other large cities. Instead, factors such as geographic location, economic specialisation, and standards of living may be more influential. Moreover, in the context of an epidemiological shock, cities with lower life expectancy appeared to exhibit greater stability compared to those with increasing life expectancy prior to the pandemic.

Conclusions and discussion

Life expectancy at birth in major Russian cities has increased in recent decades, but this growth has been uneven. Previous studies have identified a convergence of cities in terms of life expectancy during the period 2012–2019 (Shchur and Timonin 2020; Vetrova and Kalmykova 2024). This convergence was positive: large cities that initially lagged behind in life expectancy gradually approached the rising average levels observed across major cities. In this context, it is particularly important to consider the socio-economic profiles of catch-up and leading cities.

Cities were divided into groups based on life expectancy dynamics, and the main demographic and socio-economic characteristics of each group were identified. In the 0–14 age group, mortality has stabilised across all groups of cities. This age category contributes minimally to differences in life expectancy between city groups, ranging from 0.2 years in leading cities to 2.6 years in lagging cities on average over the period under review, with the leading causes of death varying from year to year.

Differences in mortality within the 15–34 age group are primarily attributable to external causes and infectious diseases. The contribution of this age group to the gap in life expectancy relative to the average ranges from 0.4 to 0.8 years.

Figure 8. Dynamics of average life expectancy in city groups relative to the overall average for all cities. *Source:* authors' compilation.

The older working-age group (35–64 years) is the most significant in terms of potential gains in life expectancy. Its contribution to the gap in life expectancy relative to the average ranges from 0.5 to 2 years. These differences are largely explained by mortality from diseases-

es of the circulatory system, a pattern consistently observed in previous studies of Russian mortality (Danilova 2017; Shchur and Timonin 2020).

While differences in life expectancy between city groups decrease in young working ages (15–34 years), they increase in the older working-age group (35–64 years).

In older age groups (65+), diseases of the circulatory system remain the dominant cause of differences in life expectancy between city groups. However, at ages 75 and older, other, less common causes of death begin to contribute most substantially.

The convergence of life expectancy from 2012 to 2019 was driven primarily by cities with populations of 100,000 to 500,000 that were not administrative centres of their regions. In contrast, the group of cities that slowed convergence consisted of large regional centres characterised by lower income levels and higher levels of air pollution. The lag of these administrative centres in life expectancy may, to some extent, be explained by migration from neighbouring territories for medical care, as well as a focus on the development of industrial enterprises and infrastructure rather than social services, healthcare institutions, or recreational facilities. However, this hypothesis requires further investigation.

The presence of large cities (over 100,000 residents) in a region does not unambiguously determine the region's ranking in terms of life expectancy, as mortality in large cities varies significantly. Within a single region, both lagging and catch-up cities may coexist, depending on their socio-economic characteristics. While urban convergence proceeded at a noticeable pace in the decade prior to the pandemic, the post-pandemic period has been marked by increasing divergence, driven not only by the direct effects of the pandemic. During the pandemic years, the greatest losses were observed in cities that had previously driven convergence – namely, cities with populations of 100,000 to 500,000 that were not regional administrative centres. Large regional centres maintained their positions as leaders or laggards, largely reflecting their pre-existing economic conditions.

Currently, statistics on Russian cities are highly fragmented, which represents the main limitation of this study. The only source of regularly collected and representative data on population income, unemployment, and education levels in cities of different sizes is the Rosstat Database of Municipalities. Behavioural factors, such as attitudes towards alcohol consumption and smoking, preferences for a healthy lifestyle, and individual characteristics of city residents, are absent from this source. Moreover, Rosstat's federal statistical observations on socio-demographic issues are not fully representative of large cities. A more comprehensive analysis of the factors that mitigate or exacerbate inequality in life expectancy between cities would be possible through an expansion of data collection at the municipal level.

Furthermore, changes to city boundaries during the period under review were not taken into account. This study relies on population and mortality data provided by Rosstat, without adjustments for the incorporation of new districts into cities, which may differ in age and sex distribution as well as in leading causes of death. The annexation of new territories thus represents an additional limitation and could be addressed in further research.

The question of the duration of convergence periods in life expectancy among large Russian cities also remains open. As studies using data from other countries have shown, the convergence process is often temporary or cyclical (Meslé and Vallin 2011). However, given the external shock of the COVID-19 pandemic, the increase in life expectancy was interrupted, and the relatively short observation period – since Rosstat only began collecting data for large cities in 2012 – precludes a thorough assessment of the potential cyclicity of convergence.

Reference list

- Adler NE, Newman K (2002) Socioeconomic disparities in health: pathways and policies. *Health affairs* 21(2): 60–76. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1377/hlthaff.21.2.60>
- Andreev E, Shkolnikov VM (2018) The relationship between mortality and economic development in Russia and its regions. *Demographic Review* 5(1): 6–24. <https://doi.org/10.17323/demreview.v5i1.7707> (in Russian)
- Andreev EM (1982) Metod komponent v analize prodolzhitel'nosti zhizni [The component method in the analysis of life expectancy]. *Bulletin of Statistics* 9: 42–7. URL: <https://www.demoscope.ru/weekly/knigi/andreev/andreev.pdf> (in Russian)
- Andreev EM (2012) On accuracy of Russia population censuses results and level of confidence in different sources of information. *Voprosy Statistiki* (11): 21–35. URL: <https://www.demoscope.ru/weekly/2013/0549/analit01.php> (in Russian)
- Andreev EM (2016) Ill-defined and unspecified causes of death in Russia. *Demographic Review* 3(2): 103–42. <https://doi.org/10.17323/demreview.v3i2.1755> (in Russian)
- Andreev EM, Kvasha EA, Kharkova TL (2014) Prodolzhitel'nost' zhizni v Rossii: vosstanovitel'nyj rost [Life expectancy in Russia: recovery growth]. *Demoscope Weekly*: (621–622). URL: <https://www.demoscope.ru/weekly/2014/0621/tema01.php> (in Russian)
- Anyanwu JC, Erhijakpor AEO (2009) Health expenditures and health outcomes in Africa. *African Development Review* 21(2): 400–33. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8268.2009.00215.x>
- Asiskovitch S (2010) Gender and health outcomes: The impact of healthcare systems and their financing on life expectancies of women and men. *Social Science & Medicine* 70(6): 886–95. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2009.11.018>
- Astrelin A (2020) Trends in morbidity, prevalence and mortality from HIV infection and tuberculosis in the regions of Russia in the XXI century. *Demographic Review* 7(4): 82–107. <https://doi.org/10.17323/demreview.v7i4.12045> (in Russian)
- Camargos MCS, Machado CJ, do Nascimento Rodrigues R (2007) Disability life expectancy for the elderly, city of São Paulo, Brazil, 2000: gender and educational differences. *Journal of Biosocial Science* 39(3): 455–63. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0021932006001428>
- Danilova IA (2017) Interregional inequality in life expectancy in Russia and its age and cause of death components. *Social Aspects of Population Health* (5): 3. <https://doi.org/10.21045/2071-5021-2017-57-5-3> (in Russian)
- Denisova IA (2018) Adult Mortality in Russia: A Microanalysis (translation: Marina Beletskaya). *Scientific Research of Faculty of Economics. Electronic Journal* 10(3): 53–89. <https://doi.org/10.38050/2078-3809-2018-10-3-53-89> (in Russian)
- Edwards RD (2011) Changes in world inequality in length of life: 1970–2000. *Population and Development Review* 37(3): 499–528. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1728-4457.2011.00432.x>
- Edwards RD, Tuljapurkar S (2005) Inequality in life spans and a new perspective on mortality convergence across industrialized countries. *Population and Development Review* 31(4): 645–74. URL: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3401520>
- Fattakhov TA, Mironova AA (2022) Population mortality in the central Russia municipalities. *Population and Economics* 6(3): 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.3897/popecon.6.e84005>
- Gazizullina PG (2018) Behavioral determinants of adolescent health in Russia. *Narodonaselenie (Population)* 21(1): 122–35. URL: https://www.isesp-ras.ru/images/narodonaselenie/2018_1.pdf (in Russian)
- Heichel S, Pape J, Sommerer T (2005) Is there convergence in convergence research? An overview of empirical studies on policy convergence. *Journal of European Public Policy* 12(5): 817–40. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13501760500161431>

- Hoi LV, Phuc HD, Dung TV et al. (2009) Remaining life expectancy among older people in a rural area of Vietnam: trends and socioeconomic inequalities during a period of multiple transitions. *BMC Public Health* 9: 471. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-9-471>
- Hrzic R, Vogt T, Brand H, Janssen F (2023) District-level mortality convergence in reunified Germany: Long-term trends and contextual determinants. *Demography* 60(1): 303–25. <https://doi.org/10.1215/00703370-10422945>
- Ivanov V, Suvorov A (2003) Problemy ohrany zdorov'ja naselenija Rossii [Problems of public health protection in Russia]. *Problems of Forecasting* 3: 99–113. URL: <https://ecfor.ru/publication/problemy-ohrany-zdorovya-naseleniya-rossii/> (in Russian)
- Jasilionis D, Shkolnikov VM (2016) Longevity and education: a demographic perspective. *Gerontology* 62(3): 253–62. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000438901>
- Kalabikhina IE, Shatalova E, Fang L (2020) Demographic situation in China: Convergence or divergence? *BRICS Journal of Economics* 1(1): 81–101. <https://doi.org/10.38050/2712-7508-2020-6>
- Karlsson M, Nilsson T, Lyttkens CH, Leeson G (2010) Income inequality and health: importance of a cross-country perspective. *Social Science & Medicine* 70(6): 875–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2009.10.056>
- Karlsson M., Nilsson T., Lyttkens C.H., Leeson G. (2010) Income inequality and health: importance of a cross-country perspective // *Social science & medicine*: 70(6), 875-85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2009.10.056>
- Kashnitsky I, de Beer J, van Wissen L (2017) Decomposition of regional convergence in population aging across Europe. *Genus* 73: 2. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41118-017-0018-2>
- Khar'kova TL, Nikitina SYu, Andreev EM (2017) Dependence of life expectancy on the education level in Russia. *Voprosy statistiki* (8): 61–9. URL: <https://voprstat.elpub.ru/jour/article/view/546> (in Russian)
- Kolosnitsyna MG, Chubarov MYu (2022) Spread of COVID-19 in the Russian regions in 2020: factors of excess mortality. *Population and Economics* 6(4): 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.3897/popecon.6.e87739>
- Kovanova ES, Badmaeva NV (2018) Migration of rural residents in Russia's regions: Issues, trends, and focus areas. *International Journal of Engineering and Technology (UAE)* 7: 288–91. <https://doi.org/10.14419/ijet.v7i4.38.24486>
- Mackenbach JP, Valverde JR, Bopp M et al. (2019) Determinants of inequalities in life expectancy: an international comparative study of eight risk factors. *The Lancet Public Health* 4(10): e529–e537. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2468-2667\(19\)30147-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2468-2667(19)30147-1)
- Marychev G, Shchur A, Timonin S (2025) Spatial-temporal comparability of mortality structure by cause of death in Russia: the role of regional cause-of-death coding practices. *Demographic Review* 12(3): 59–105. <https://doi.org/10.17323/demreview.v12i3.28497> (in Russian)
- Maximov MA (2025) Cohort effect in mortality from HIV and tuberculosis in Russia. *Population and Economics* 9(4): 115–27. <https://doi.org/10.3897/popecon.9.e160028>
- Meara ER, Richards S, Cutler DM (2008) The gap gets bigger: changes in mortality and life expectancy, by education, 1981–2000. *Health Affairs* 27(2): 350–60. <https://doi.org/10.1377/hlthaff.27.2.350>
- Meslé F, Shkolnikov VM (1999) Smertnost' v Rossii: zatjanuvsheesja ostavanie [Mortality in Russia: a protracted lag]. *World of Russia* 8(4): 138–62. URL: <https://mirros.hse.ru/article/view/5408> (in Russian)
- Meslé F, Vallin J (2011) Historical trends in mortality // In: Rogers R, Crimmins E (eds) *International Handbook of Adult Mortality*. *International Handbooks of Population*, vol 2. Springer, Dordrecht, 9–47. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-90-481-9996-9_2

- Mkrtchyan NV (2012) Problemy ucheta naselenija otdel'nyh vozrastnyh grupp v hode perepisi naselenija 2010 g.: prichiny otklonenij poluchennyh dannyh ot ozhidaemyh [Problems of accounting for the population of individual age groups during the 2010 population census: reasons for deviations of the obtained data from the expected ones]. In: Denisenko MB (ed.) Demographic aspects of socio-economic development. Series: Demographic studies, issue 22. M.: MAX Press, 197–214. URL: <https://www.demoscope.ru/weekly/2014/0581/analit02.php> (in Russian)
- Nikoloski Z, Shkolnikov VM, Mossialos E (2023) Preventable mortality in the Russian Federation: a retrospective, regional level study. *The Lancet Regional Health – Europe* 29: 100631. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lanep.2023.100631>
- Noy S, Sprague-Jones J (2016) Comparative dynamics of public health spending: Re-conceptualizing delta-convergence to examine OECD and Latin America. *International Journal of Comparative Sociology* 57(6): 425–48. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002071521668682>
- Panin AN, Tikunov VS, Eshrokov VM, Vatlina TV (2023) Geoinformation analysis Russian health system: modeling, visualization, analysis. *Population and Economics* 7(3): 136–71. <https://doi.org/10.3897/popecon.7.e104639>
- Pyankova A, Fattakhov T (2017) Mortality by educational level in Russia. *HSE Economic Journal* 21(4): 623–47. URL: <https://ej.hse.ru/data/2017/12/28/1160683586/Пьянкова.pdf> (in Russian)
- Revich BA (2005) Rol' okruzhajushhej sredy kak faktora smertnosti naselenija Rossii [The role of the environment as a factor in mortality of the population of Russia]. *Demoscope Weekly* (227–228). URL: <https://www.demoscope.ru/weekly/2005/0227/analit02.php> (in Russian)
- Revich BA (2018) Fine suspended particulates in ambient air and their health effects in megapolises. *Problems of Environmental Monitoring and Modeling of Ecosystems* 29(3): 53–78. <https://doi.org/10.21513/0207-2564-2018-3-53-78> (in Russian)
- Revich BA, Kuznetsova OV, Kharkova TL, Podolnaya MA (2019) Jekonomicheskie faktory differenciacii rossijskih megapolisov po urovnju smertnosti [Economic factors differentiating Russian megacities by mortality rate]. *Social Aspects of Population Health* 65(3). <https://doi.org/10.21045/2071-5021-2019-65-3-5> (in Russian)
- Safarova GL, Kalmykova NM, Safarova AA (2018) Contribution of Senior Age Groups to Changes in Life Expectancy Indicators for Russia's Megalopolises (Moscow and St. Petersburg). *Advances in Gerontology* 8: 263–70. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S2079057018040148>
- Savina AA, Lukmanov AS, Zemlyanova EV (2023) HIV-mortality trends in the regions of Russian Federation. *HIV Infection and Immunosuppressive Disorders* 15(2): 81–9. <https://doi.org/10.22328/2077-9828-2023-15-2-81-89> (in Russian)
- Sede PI, Ohemeng W (2015) Socio-economic determinants of life expectancy in Nigeria (1980–2011). *Health Economics Review* 5: 2. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13561-014-0037-z>
- Shchur A, Shkolnikov VM, Timonin S, Andreev E, Leon DA (2021) Where do people live longer in Russia in the 21st century? Life expectancy across urban and rural areas. *Population and Development Review* 47(4): 1049–74. <https://doi.org/10.1111/padr.12437>
- Shchur A, Sokolova V, Timonin S (2023) Midlife mortality in Russia at the beginning of the 21st century: is there any reason for optimism? *Demographic Review* 10(4): 4–51. <https://doi.org/10.17323/demreview.v10i4.18807>
- Shchur A, Timonin S (2020) Center-peripheral differences in life expectancy in Russia: regional analysis. *Demographic Review* 7(3): 108–33. <https://doi.org/10.17323/demreview.v7i3.11638> (in Russian)
- Shchur AE (2018) Cities of over a million people on the mortality map of Russia. *Demographic Review* 5(4): 66–91. <https://doi.org/10.17323/demreview.v5i4.8663> (in Russian)

- Shkolnikov VM, Andreev EM, Jasilionis D et al. (2006) The changing relation between education and life expectancy in central and eastern Europe in the 1990s. *Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health* 60(10): 875–81. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16973535/>
- Shkolnikov VM, Andreev EM, Zhang Z, Oeppen J, Vaupel JW (2011) Losses of expected lifetime in the United States and other developed countries: methods and empirical analyses. *Demography* 48(1): 211–39. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13524-011-0015-6>
- Timonin S, Danilova I, Andreev E et al. (2017) Recent mortality trend reversal in Russia: are regions following the same tempo? *European Journal of Population* 33: 733–63. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10680-017-9451-3>
- Timonin S, Jasilionis D, Shkolnikov VM, Andreev E (2020) New perspective on geographical mortality divide in Russia: a district-level cross-sectional analysis, 2008–2012. *Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health* 74(2): 144–50. <https://doi.org/10.1136/jech-2019-213239>
- van den Heuvel WJA, Olaroiu M (2017) How important are health care expenditures for life expectancy? A comparative, European analysis. *Journal of the American Medical Directors Association* 18(3): 276.e9–276.e12. URL: [https://www.jamda.com/article/S1525-8610\(16\)30559-X/pdf](https://www.jamda.com/article/S1525-8610(16)30559-X/pdf)
- Vetrova E, Kalmykova N (2024) Convergence of mortality rates and life expectancy in Russia's major cities before and after the pandemic. *Demographic Review* 11(2): 4–20. <https://doi.org/10.17323/demreview.v11i2.21824>
- Zimmer Z, Amornsirisomboon P (2001) Socioeconomic status and health among older adults in Thailand: an examination using multiple indicators. *Social Science & Medicine* 52(8): 1297–311. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0277-9536\(00\)00232-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0277-9536(00)00232-x)

Other sources of information

- Air pollution in Russian cities since 2007 (2023) // Roshydromet; processed by “To Be Precise” URL: https://tochno.st/datasets/air_cities
- Database of indicators of municipalities: combined and processed data for 2006–2020 // Rosstat; processing: Vedenkov M.V., Komin M.O., Tsygankov M.V., Infrastructure of scientific research data. ANO “CPUR”, 2022. URL: <http://data.rcsi.science/data-catalog/datasets/115/>
- WHO (2018) Ambient (outdoor) air pollution. URL: <https://www.undrr.org/understanding-disaster-risk/terminology/hips/en0003> (accessed: 10.10.2024)

Information about the authors

- Vetrova Ekaterina Dmitrievna – Assistant at the Department of Mathematical Methods for Economics. Faculty of Economics of Lomonosov Moscow State University. Moscow, 119991, Russia. Email: ekat.vetrova@gmail.com
- Kalmykova Natalia Mikhailovna – Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor of the Department of Population. Faculty of Economics of Lomonosov Moscow State University. Moscow, 119991, Russia. Email: natalia-kalmykova@yandex.ru
- Mikhail Antonovich Maximov – PhD student. Faculty of Economics of Lomonosov Moscow State University. Moscow, 119991, Russia. E-mail: mihailmaximov000@gmail.com

Appendix

Table A1. Complete list of Russian cities with populations over 100,000 in 2011, classified by life expectancy dynamics.

Region	City	Population size category	Life expectancy dynamics category
Altai Krai	Barnaul	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
	Biysk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Rubtsovsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
Amur Oblast	Blagoveshchensk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
Arkhangelsk Oblast	Severodvinsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	b. Decreasing advantage
Astrakhan Oblast	Astrakhan	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
Belgorod Oblast	Belgorod	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	b. Decreasing advantage
	Stary Oskol	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	b. Decreasing advantage
Bryansk Oblast	Bryansk	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Vladimir	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
Vladimir Oblast	Kovrov	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Murom	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
Volgograd Oblast	Volgograd	city with a population of over a million	a. Increasing advantage
	Volzhsky	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	b. Decreasing advantage
	Kamyshin	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
Vologda Oblast	Vologda	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
	Cherepovets	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
Voronezh Oblast	Voronezh	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	b. Decreasing advantage

Region	City	Population size category	Life expectancy dynamics category
Transbaikal Krai	Chita	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
Ivanovo Oblast	Ivanovo	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
	Irkutsk	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
Irkutsk Oblast	Angarsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Bratsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
Kabardino-Balkarian Republic	Nalchik	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	b. Decreasing advantage
Kaliningrad Oblast	Kaliningrad	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
	Kaluga	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
Kaluga Oblast	Obninsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
Kamchatka Krai	Petropavlovsk-Kamchatsky	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
Karachay-Cherkess Republic	Cherkessk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
	Kemerovo	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
Kemerovo Oblast – Kuzbass	Novokuznetsk	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Prokopyevsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
Kirov Oblast	Kirov	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	b. Decreasing advantage
Kostroma Oblast	Kostroma	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
	Krasnodar	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
Krasnodar Krai	Armavir	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
	Novorossiysk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
	Sochi	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage

Region	City	Population size category	Life expectancy dynamics category
	Krasnoyarsk	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
Krasnoyarsk Krai	Achinsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Norilsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
Kurgan Oblast	Kurgan	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
Kursk Oblast	Kursk	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
Lipetsk Oblast	Lipetsk	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
	Yelets	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
Moscow	Moscow	city with a population of over a million	a. Increasing advantage
	Zhukovsky	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
	Sergiev Posad	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Korolev	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
	Kolomna	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Lyubertsy	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Mytishchi	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
Moscow Oblast	Noginsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Odintsovo	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
	Orekhovo-Zuyevo	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Podolsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
	Serpukhov	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Khimki	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage

Region	City	Population size category	Life expectancy dynamics category
Moscow Oblast	Shchelkovo	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Elektrostal	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Krasnogorsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
Murmansk Oblast	Pushkino	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Murmansk	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
Nizhny Novgorod Oblast	Nizhny Novgorod	city with a population of over a million	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Arzamas	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
Novgorod Oblast	Dzerzhinsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Veliky Novgorod	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
Novosibirsk Oblast	Novosibirsk	city with a population of over a million	d. Increasing disadvantage
Omsk Oblast	Omsk	city with a population of over a million	d. Increasing disadvantage
Orenburg Oblast	Orenburg	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
	Orsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
Oryol Oblast	Oryol	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
Penza Oblast	Penza	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	b. Decreasing advantage
Perm Krai	Perm	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Berezniki	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
Primorsky Krai	Vladivostok	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Artem	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Nakhodka	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
	Ussuriysk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage

Region	City	Population size category	Life expectancy dynamics category
Pskov Oblast	Pskov	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
Republic of Adygea (Adygea)	Maykop	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
	Ufa	city with a population of over a million	a. Increasing advantage
	Neftekamsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
Republic of Bashkortostan	Octyabrsky	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
	Salavat	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Sterlitamak	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
Republic of Buryatia	Ulan-Ude	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Makhachkala	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
Republic of Dagestan	Derbent	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
	Kaspiysk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
	Khasavyurt	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
Republic of Kalmykia	Elista	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
Republic of Karelia	Petrozavodsk	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
Komi Republic	Sykt'yvkar	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	b. Decreasing advantage
Republic of Mari El	Yoshkar-Ola	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
Republic of Mordovia	Saransk	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
Republic of Sakha (Yakutia)	Yakutsk	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
Republic of North Ossetia-Alania	Vladikavkaz	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage

Region	City	Population size category	Life expectancy dynamics category
	Kazan	city with a population of over a million	a. Increasing advantage
Republic of Tatarstan (Tatarstan)	Almetyevsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
	Naberezhnye Chelny	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	b. Decreasing advantage
	Nizhnekamsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	b. Decreasing advantage
Republic of Tuva	Kyzyl	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
Republic of Khakassia	Abakan	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Rostov-on-Don	city with a population of over a million	b. Decreasing advantage
	Bataysk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
Rostov Oblast	Volgodonsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	b. Decreasing advantage
	Novocherkassk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
	Novoshakhtinsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Taganrog	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
	Shakhty	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
Ryazan Oblast	Ryazan	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
Samara Oblast	Samara	city with a population of over a million	d. Increasing disadvantage
	Novokuibyshevsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Syzran	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Tolyatti	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
Saint Petersburg	Saint Petersburg	city with a population of over a million	a. Increasing advantage
Saratov Oblast	Saratov	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage

Region	City	Population size category	Life expectancy dynamics category
Saratov Oblast	Balakovo	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Engels	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
Sakhalin Oblast	Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Yekaterinburg	city with a population of over a million	a. Increasing advantage
Sverdlovsk Oblast	Kamensk-Uralsky	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Nizhny Tagil	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
Smolensk Oblast	Pervouralsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
	Smolensk	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
	Stavropol	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	b. Decreasing advantage
Stavropol Krai	Essentuki	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
	Kislovodsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	b. Diminishing advantage
	Nevinnomyssk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
	Pyatigorsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
Tambov Oblast	Tambov	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
Tver Oblast	Tver	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
Tomsk Oblast	Tomsk	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
	Seversk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	b. Decreasing advantage
Tula Oblast	Tula	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Novomoskovsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
Tyumen Oblast	Tyumen	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage

Region	City	Population size category	Life expectancy dynamics category
Udmurt Republic	Izhevsk	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
Ulyanovsk Oblast	Ulyanovsk	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	b. Diminishing advantage
	Dimitrovgrad	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
Khabarovsk Krai	Khabarovsk	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
	Komsomolsk-on-Amur	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Nefteyugansk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Okrug	Nizhnevartovsk	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	b. Decreasing advantage
	Surgut	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
	Chelyabinsk	city with a population of over a million	d. Increasing disadvantage
	Zlatoust	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
Chelyabinsk Oblast	Kopeysk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Magnitogorsk	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
	Miass	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
Chechen Republic	Grozny	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage
Chuvash Republic – Chuvashia	Cheboksary	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	b. Diminishing advantage
	Novocheboksarsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
Yamalo-Nenets Autonomous Okrug	Novy Urengoy	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	a. Increasing advantage
	Noyabrsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	b. Decreasing advantage
Yaroslavl Oblast	Yaroslavl	large city (more than 250 thousand people)	d. Increasing disadvantage
	Rybinsk	big city (more than 100 thousand people)	c. Decreasing disadvantage

Source: compiled by the authors

Figure A1. Dominant cause of death contributing most to the excess life expectancy above the average, men, “increasing advantage” city group, 2011–2019. *Source:* Compiled by the authors based on Rosstat data. *Note:* The cells of the matrix indicate the total contribution of each age group to the excess of life expectancy above the average level

Figure A2. Dominant cause of death contributing most to the excess life expectancy above the average, women, “increasing advantage” city group, 2011–2019. *Source:* Compiled by the authors based on Rosstat data. *Note:* The cells of the matrix indicate the total contribution of each age group to the excess of life expectancy above the average level

Figure A3. Dominant cause of death contributing most to the excess life expectancy above the average, men, “decreasing advantage” city group, 2011–2019. *Source:* Compiled by the authors based on Rosstat data. *Note:* The cells of the matrix indicate the total contribution of each age group to the excess of life expectancy above the average level

Figure A4. Dominant cause of death contributing most to the excess life expectancy above the average, women, “decreasing advantage” city group, 2011–2019. *Source:* Compiled by the authors based on Rosstat data. *Note:* The cells of the matrix indicate the total contribution of each age group to the excess of life expectancy above the average level

Figure A5. Dominant cause of death contributing most to the lag in life expectancy relative to the average, men, “decreasing disadvantage” city group, 2011–2019. *Source:* Compiled by the authors based on Rosstat data. *Note:* The cells of the matrix indicate the total contribution of each age group to the lag in life expectancy relative to the average level

Figure A6. Dominant cause of death contributing most to the lag in life expectancy relative to the average, women, “decreasing disadvantage” city group, 2011–2019. *Source:* Compiled by the authors based on Rosstat data. *Note:* The cells of the matrix indicate the total contribution of each age group to the lag in life expectancy relative to the average level

Figure A7. Dominant cause of death contributing most to the lag in life expectancy relative to the average, men, “increasing disadvantage” city group, 2011–2019. *Source:* Compiled by the authors based on Rosstat data. *Note:* The cells of the matrix indicate the total contribution of each age group to the lag in life expectancy relative to the average level

Figure A8. Dominant cause of death contributing most to the lag in life expectancy relative to the average, women, “increasing disadvantage” city group, 2011–2019. *Source:* Compiled by the authors based on Rosstat data. *Note:* The cells of the matrix indicate the total contribution of each age group to the lag in life expectancy relative to the average level

Figure A9. Decomposition of the lag in life expectancy at birth between large cities and the average level by cause of death, 0–14 years, 2012–2019 (enlarged chart). *Source:* Compiled by the authors based on Rosstat data